

Cultural Focus as an Important Factor Creating Scientific Elites and the Absence of Its Reflection in Scientometrics

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One of the criteria for the selection of scientific elites is the cultural focus of their research. It should focus on phenomena relevant to large cultures to gain wider publicity. The importance of such a criterion for scientific elite selection might be lessened if a scientometric metric is used to measure the cultural focus and reflects it. As shown by the metrics included on the web page Metrics Toolkit the metrics offered by the scientometric community do not include such a measure.

Some academic disciplines cover issues connected to both natural and cultural sciences, one such discipline being psychology. In the psychology departments of major Korean universities, approximately 95% of professors were educated in the United States. While fostering scientific careers of only those educated in one concrete foreign country might seem as strange, it is actually logical. These scientists are better at focusing their research on issues relevant to a larger scientific community. If their research were focused on phenomena relevant primarily in Korea, it would reach a smaller audience than when focused on issues relevant to a larger community. This resulted in a halt in indigenous psychological research in Korea during 2010s.

Cultural focus on issues relevant for large cultures is important for researchers, because audience-based metrics prevail in academic research evaluation. Research that garners larger appreciation is considered better. Evaluators could include cultural focus among the criteria for research evaluation, potentially benefitting those culturally focused on smaller cultures, if the scientometric community offers metrics for cultural focus measurement. Currently, this is not the case. As seen in the metrics included in Metrics Toolkit, all are focused on audience size.

The metrics count attention, mentions, citations, downloads, and the number of libraries holding

the publication. If these metrics are weighted, it is by subject category or year of publication, not by the size of the potential audience interested in the specific cultural focus. These metrics disadvantage researchers whose focus is on themes of interest only to people from smaller cultures. The only type of metric included in the Metrics Toolkit that does not disadvantage these researchers are those based on peer reviews. However, none of the offered metrics is able to measure the cultural focus of a publication.

Research evaluators typically use metrics based on audience size. When no metrics measuring cultural focus are offered to them, researchers focusing on smaller cultures are evaluated as being inferior despite the high quality of their research. This creates a need to develop metrics to measure cultural focus. One such metric is the Linguistic Diversity Index based on languages cited in the publication. However, this metric is nearly impossible to use with current databases due to insufficient coverage of publications written in lesser-used languages. Artificial intelligence might bring new possibilities for measuring cultural focus if it is trained to track the cultural uniqueness of words and terminology used in publications. The use of such a metric in research evaluation could break the monopoly of global/US-culture focused researchers on becoming members of the scientific elite.

One of the most crucial criteria for the selection of scientific elites is the provision of scientometric metrics by the scientometric community. If measures based on cultural focus are developed, it will allow research evaluators to use them, thus creating an environment where scientists focusing on smaller cultures can continue to work and excel in their fields.